

The Effects of the Covid-19 Pandemic on Sport and Change-Event on Athlete Performance

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to investigate the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on sports, its industry and competitions, and its impact on the psychological state of athletes and sports fans. After the world suffered from the spread of the Corona pandemic "Covid 19" and its various effects on humans, as it was classified by the World Health Organization as one of the pandemic diseases that spread quickly, widely and rapidly and that led to human losses. Covid 19 led to the adoption of a set of health measures, the most important of which was quarantine as a preventive measure aimed at limiting the spread of infection, and this led to huge losses in global markets, the energy sector, the economy, tourism and entertainment. The sports field was not excluded from these repercussions, as it is an important sector on the economic, sports and social levels, the sports sector has been particularly affected by the Covid -19 crisis in a way we have not seen before, with all physical activities, face-to-face, and all team sports suddenly being restricted indefinitely in many countries. And this change is significant for most male and female athletes professionals and non-professionals competing in various tournaments, and as a result, sports organizations have had to restructure themselves to provide a service to their users. The coronavirus pandemic has caused the biggest disruption to the global sporting calendar since World War II worldwide with varying degrees of postponement of sporting events so that spectators do not have matches to watch and players do not have matches to play. Turkmenistan, Belarus, Nicaragua, and Tajikistan are among the countries that have continued to hold professional sports contests as scheduled. The Arctic Winter Games have been canceled for 2020, whereas the ASEAN Olympic Games have been rescheduled for 2020.

KEYWORDS: Corona pandemic, global sporting, psychological state of athletes, sports fans, Olympic Games

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1- INTRODUCTION

Since countries declared public emergencies due to the entry of an intruder virus coming from China during the period from February to March 2020, the economic, social and health sectors have begun to be affected one by one, and the state of panic is rising little by little as a result of the outbreak of a new disease, Covid19, which was declared by the World Health Organization as a global pandemic. which led to human losses. And, as a result of its economic and social implications, it wreaked havoc on society, with particularly severe ramifications in the sports business. Many communities experienced periods of isolation and reduced economic activity as a result of the lockdown. Sports

activities have been halted due to the shutdown (Abrams & Szeffler, 2020).

For many athletes (athletes, coaches, and referees), the year 2020 was meant to be the pinnacle year, when their aspirations and abilities would be achieved. The development of the Corona virus pandemic, which resulted in quarantine and closures, social isolation, and the suspension of commercial flights, had a significant influence on the world of sports, as players were unable to practice, compete, or go to international gatherings (Jason& Nell, 2020).

Because of this, most major sporting events for 2020, such as the Tokyo Olympics (OGs), the European Football Championships, and Wimbledon tennis, have been postponed

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or eventually canceled. Athletes' lives have changed dramatically (Henriksen *et al.*, 2019). Their lifestyle, daily routine, and financial situation (loss of a job or sponsor) have changed (Altena *et al.*, 2020). People infected with Coronavirus 2019 (Covid-19) suffer from many concerns, including health, insecurity, and performance and employment. Sports coaches and referees have struggled with the pandemic as their sporting participation and career paths change, and they feel less important than they used to. Face a group of injury and quarantine rulers, and stay away from families and loved ones, less communication with colleagues and friends (BBC Sport, 2020; Taku and Arai, 2020).

The postponement of the Olympic and Paralympic Games represents a major occupational disorder. Although this new situation is considered a "transition of the crisis," on the other hand, it affected sports makers and athletes and had other negative side effects on the participants such as decreased sleep, appetite, loneliness, and fear of an uncertain future. Certainly for the Olympics (Byrd *et al.*, 2020). The Association for Applied Sports Psychology (AASP) states that athletes may suffer from an emotional roller coaster due to disruption of their daily routine, which may affect them psychologically in all aspects. This organization has also published practical recommendations for athletes and exercisers to maintain effective mental health and support during this period (Schinke *et al.*, 2020).

(Pillay *et al.*, 2020) conducted a survey of a group of athletes via the Internet. Athletes explained that their sleep patterns changed during the quarantine and that a large number of athletes consumed large amounts of carbohydrates. Most of them tried to train on their own, and most of them confirmed that they felt depressed and struggled to motivate themselves to exercise.

The effects were harmful and normal sporting events (football, basketball, Asian Basketball League, Biathlon World Cup, bodybuilding, etc.) were not held. The important players in the sports supply chain have suffered unimaginable harm (such as teams, sponsors, hotels, airlines, and carriers). In addition, related industries that depend directly or indirectly on sports have halted or shut down their operations. Many of these companies have closed or likely never open again. Therefore, it is assumed that the adjustments will lead to a permanent transformation of the sports industry. This could radically change the patterns of sports activity (Clemente-Suárez *et al.*, 2020).

Many employment are at stake throughout the world as a result of Covid-19, including those in retail and sports services related with tournaments and events, such as travel, tourism, infrastructure, transportation, catering, and worldwide broadcasting. As a result, all sorts of sports businesses must adjust their business strategies to changing environmental conditions (Taku and Arai, 2020). Sports and athletes suffered in the shadow of the pandemic and were affected greatly and clearly. In this article, the suffering of

sports in the conditions of the pandemic and its effects on athletes and the sport-loving public will be highlighted.

2- COVID-19 PANDEMIC

The Corona Covid-19 pandemic is one of the epidemics that afflicted humanity, and it is not the first, as many peoples have passed through pandemics such as the Spanish flu in the year 1918-1919, or the SARS virus (2002-2003), which is considered Covid-19. As an extension of it, virus, swine flu, or Ebola are all serious diseases and viruses that threaten global societies, except for the repercussions of the Corona virus were the largest in the world (Bouamoucha, 2020)

3- THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON SPORTS COMPETITIONS

The Arctic Winter Games have been canceled for 2020, whereas the ASEAN Olympic Games have been rescheduled for 2020. Tokyo was supposed to host the 2020 Summer Olympics starting in late July. The Japanese government has taken extra safeguards in preparation for the forthcoming Olympics to try limit the outbreak's worst effects. Qualifying events, on the other hand, are practically daily canceled or postponed. In light of the issue, there have been proposals that the 2020 Olympics be moved to London, although Tokyo Governor Yuriko Koike stated at the end of February 2020 that such a relocation was not presently being considered. Without spectators, the traditional Olympic torch-lighting ritual was performed in Olympia, Greece on March 12 to commemorate the opening of the 2020 Summer Olympics (BBC sport, 2020; Fitzsimmons & Caitlin, 2020).

In Saudi Arabia, the Ministry of Sports announced on March 14, 2020, the suspension of sports activity in various sports and all tournaments and competitions, as well as the closure of private gyms and sports centers, starting from Sunday, March 15, 2020 AD until further notice. As a result of the virus, the Chinese Super League for 2020 has been postponed. A handful of group stage matches in the 2020 AFC Champions League and AFC Cup were also rescheduled. Due to the epidemic, FIFA and the Asian Football Confederation confirmed on March 9, 2020 that the 2022 FIFA World Cup qualifiers, which were planned for March and June 2020, will be postponed to a later date. The qualifying matches between South Korea and China in the 2020 AFC Women's Olympic Qualifying Championships have also been postponed (Wagner & James 2020; Campbell *et al.*, 2020).

In Europe, several Champions League and Europa League knockout matches were played behind closed doors in February and March 2020. ("Athletes warned against excessive celebrations at Tokyo 2020; "Tokyo 2020 organizers publish first set of rules to ensure Games can go ahead, 2021). The Champions League matches (Manchester City vs Real Madrid, and Juventus vs Lyon), and the two Europa League matches (Inter vs Getafe and Seville vs Roma) were postponed indefinitely. The inaugural season of

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the CAF Basketball League has been postponed from March 2020 to an undisclosed date due to the coronavirus pandemic (Simon, 2021)

The 2019-2020 season of the Chinese Basketball Association was suspended on February 1, 2020 (Gallagher *et al.*, 2021). On February 14, the International Basketball Federation (FIBA) ordered the postponement of two AFC Asian Cup preliminaries until further notice, the Philippines vs. Thailand in Quezon City, and Japan vs. China in Chiba. Due to the coronavirus pandemic, many AFL sports events for the 2019-2020 season that were supposed to be held starting from February have been rescheduled (Bruton, & Michelle 2021).

Jordi Bertomeu, the European League's CEO, has suspended matches between 14 March and 11 April. The European League earlier suspended the European Basketball Association, and the International Basketball Federation (FIBA) suspended the European Basketball Champions League and European Basketball European Cup from March 14. The Lithuanian, Swedish, Swiss, Slovak, and Ukrainian Basketball League canceled the first round of their respective leagues completely, with the championship awarded to the top teams. (SwimSwam 2020).

The Australian Basketball League final matches between the Sydney Kings and Berth Wildcats were played in a closed court starting with the second game, and the Australian Basketball League said it would suspend matches immediately if a player was diagnosed with the disease (Bruton, & Michelle 2020b). The Biathlon World Cup for the 2019-20 season finished a week and a day early than expected. The World Cup final in Norway, like the previous World Cup final in Finland, was canceled (Sawatzky & Mike 2020).

Many competitive events in international bodybuilding at junior or professional levels have seen restrictions, postponements or cancellations due to concerns about the spread of Covid -19. On March 16, 2020, Jim Manion, president of the International Federation of Bodybuilding and Fitness and the National Bodybuilding Commission announced that competitions scheduled for May 10, 2020 in the United States would be postponed until another date during the year or canceled until the 2021 season (Ethier & Matt, 2020).

Promotion for the main event of the Ultimate Fighting Championship between Lee and Oliveira that was scheduled to take place on March 13 in Brasilia, Brazil continued, and the organizers planned to hold it in an indoor arena without spectators. The UFC supervisors then announced on March 16 that the next three events would be postponed until future dates to be determined (Schad & Tom 2020; Joseph & Andrew 2020).

In reaction to the epidemic, the Canadian Football League (CFL) stated on March 12th that a number of league-wide preparation activities will be canceled or modified. In reaction to the epidemic, several professional and amateur golf tournaments, including the major championships, have been postponed or canceled. On March 13th, (Solomon & Salem, 2020).

Due to the epidemic, the majority of Asian, European, African, and American nations postponed most of their planned sports events, with just a few countries, such as Turkmenistan, Belarus, Nicaragua, and Tajikistan, continuing their professional sports fixtures as scheduled (Cooper *et al.*, 2020). In table some Examples of sporting events has changed over the past 10 days due to coronavirus infection

Table 1: Examples of sporting events has changed over the past some days due to coronavirus infection

Date	Competition
25/3	DIVING: The London leg of the 2020 Fina Diving World Series has been canceled by British Swimming. It had been postponed at first. FOOTBALL: The suspension of Japan's J League, as well as the accompanying cup tournament, has been prolonged until May. UNICEF's Soccer Aid fundraiser, which was set to take place on June 6 at Old Trafford, has been postponed. MOTORSPORT: The British Superbike Championship's first three rounds—at Silverstone, Oulton Park, and Donington Park—have been postponed.
23/3	BOXING: The British iBoxing Board of Control has put a hold on all competitions until the end of April. FOOTBALL: All football in Spain, including La Liga, has been suspended indefinitely due to the spread of the coronavirus. FOOTBALL: The Irish Football Association has extended the suspension of the Northern Ireland football season until April 30. Uefa has postponed the Champions League and Europa League finals, which were slated for May 30 and 27, respectively, as well as the Women's Champions League final, which was set for May 24. FORMULA 1: The Azerbaijan Grand Prix, scheduled for June 7, has been postponed or canceled for the ninth time in the 2020 season. RUGBY LEAGUE: The National Rugby League of Australia, which has been held behind closed doors, has been stopped.
16/3	ATHLETICS: All 675 Parkrun events in the United Kingdom have been halted, at least until the end of March. BASEBALL: A Cincinnati Reds employee at their Arizona spring training facility tested positive for coronavirus.

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4- PSYCHOLOGICAL RISKS FOR ATHLETES RESULTING FROM LIFESTYLE CHANGES DUE TO COVID-19.

The whole world is suffering from the aftermath of the outbreak of the new Corona virus, which has placed nearly three billion people in quarantine, but athletes face additional risks that affect mental health as a result of their transition from a very active lifestyle to isolation and boredom (Dong, and Bouey, 2020).

Although some of the athletes stuck behind closed doors due to the curfew and the postponement or cancellation of all local, continental and international tournaments, showed some optimism by posting videos of themselves training or taking on Internet challenges, the pressure caused by adapting to the emerging reality and the uncertain future may have its impact (Mehrsafar *et al.*, 2020).

The medical officer of the Australian Tennis Association, Caroline Broderick, told AFP that the long-term impact of epidemics such as SARS and swine flu on athletes, such as severe anxiety, obsession with washing hands and fear of approaching people(Pillay *et al.*, 2020).But the impact of the current epidemic is unprecedented, especially after all sports activities around the world stopped due to the "Covid-19" virus, which the World Health Organization classified as a pandemic, after it infected the whole world, and the number of deaths as of Tuesday morning reached nearly 38,000 people out of about 800,000 infections(Mehrsafar *et al.*,2020).

Athletes were not spared the negative effects of this virus, whether they were of the level of American tennis legend Serena Williams, who had previously suffered from depression during her career, or promising stars who were looking forward to what awaits them this summer in the Summer Olympics before the decision was taken to postpone it until Summer 2021 as a result of "Covid-19."Serena, the 38-year-old who needs a single big title in order to equal the absolute record for the number of Grand Slam titles recorded in the name of Australian Margaret Court (Qiu *et al.*, 2017), admitted that the social separation due to the virus caused her "a lot of stress." And she indicated, through the "Tik Tok" application, that "every incoming and outgoing drives me crazy. By severe anxiety, I mean that I am on the edge of the abyss. Any time someone around me sneezes or coughs, I feel crazy"(Pillay *et al.*, 2020).

Even before the virus, top athletes suffered from depression caused by fatigue, stress and physical and mental demands, from Serena to her compatriots, swimming and Olympic legend Michael Phelps, former mixed martial arts champion Ronda Rousey and former boxing legend Mike Tyson, all the way to former New Zealand rugby star John Kirwan. 'I suffer in my own way'. The decision to postpone the Olympic Games in Tokyo until the summer of 2021 is sure to have a negative impact on the thousands of athletes who have put aside their daily jobs in order to prepare themselves for this most important event for any athlete. This

is the case of American weightlifter Kate Nye, who admitted to "WoodTV" that "I would be lying if I said I'm fine. Like most people, I struggle in my own ways," referring to her diagnosis of bipolar disorder. Concerns have also been raised about Australian swimmers and cricketers, after athletes in both sports have suffered documented psychological problems in the past (Samuel *et al.*, 2020).

Caroline Broderick, who previously served as Australia's deputy medical director at the 2016 Rio Olympics and now serves as a member of the National Rugby League advisory committee in addition to her job as a medical officer for Tennis Australia, said the effects of isolation could be even more severe for athletes. She explained, "They suffer from the same psychological problems that everyone else suffers from, but they also suffer from stress and anxiety about their future, which is something they cannot control easily. They do not know what the next stage is or how long they will remain in quarantine or isolation."

Many sports bodies have moved to provide support to athletes, but there are some sports that have resorted to reducing salaries in order to avoid huge financial losses in light of the suspension of tournaments, which reduces their ability to psychological help (Pillay *et al.*, 2020). Broderick considered drug use or excessive alcohol consumption as a clear sign of problems, explaining, "Stress and anxiety can manifest in drug use. This is what I would look for (signals), if they were using alcohol as a support". "There has certainly been some concern," Broderick said. "The top professional athletes can deal with a loss of income, but there are a lot of athletes on the sidelines (in terms of financial capacity). If you don't play for a few months, there is a huge loss of income as well."(Toresdahl, and Asif 2020). Broderick recommends that athletes stick to a routine, focus on what they can control, and use free time to pursue a hobby or train online to maintain their mental health.

5- THE EFFECTS OF THE CORONA PANDEMIC ON SPORTS FANS

Most sports fans are eagerly awaiting the next day, the day they have been waiting for a long time, the day their favorite team will play the Champions League final. They are eagerly waiting for this meeting, imagining with joy when their team scores, when the referee blows his whistle, how they feel when the captain raises the cup, it will undoubtedly be an influential moment, and what doubles the enthusiasm this time is that they will live in this atmosphere from the field. Watching from the field of play has a special effect and a special impact (World Health Organization, 2019).

Well, let's go back to the center of what happened in 2020, the Corona virus, which scientists tell us we have a long period of struggle with, and most optimists do not expect it to be over before at least a year, which is the time when the vaccine is supposed to come out or we can find a protocol My treatment enables us to raise the recovery rate, and until we reach one of them, we will spend this period in skirmishes with the virus; Sometimes a temporary silence and a fierce

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wave at other times, so we will not be able in any way to return to our normal life during this period. All areas of life were affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, including sports, stadiums were closed for periods and competitions were postponed (Lauer *et al.*, 2019).

The only point that no one asked about is the fate of the audience, given that the answer to the question is more than intuitive, because if we accept that the return of football is inevitable because it will not be able to bear the losses of stopping for a longer period, the audience is not like that, and thousands of people are sitting in one place like the stands for a period of time Long is an ideal environment for the virus to spread again and it contradicts the simplest rules of social distancing. Therefore, as long as the world has not found a vaccine, the public will not return to the stands, no matter how long it takes. Perhaps this is the new reality that we must adapt to; Football with empty stands (Wang *et al.*, 2019).

It would be difficult to keep stadiums empty all the time, and a match in the Borussia Dortmund stadium without the usual hustle of the southern stand would affect the performance of the players as part of the psychological factors influencing, and no one would like to play Liverpool and not hear their eternal fans anthem "you will never walk alone". Football without an audience is not the best option, and it may not be necessary at all, as Pep Guardiola says, However, it may be the most that can be achieved during the pandemic, because if we wait until the public can attend, then the economic losses may have eliminated football completely. This period of absence is an opportunity to think about the idea of the audience attending the matches from the beginning, and it prompts us to think about it more comprehensively even after the return and the end of Corona, which will not be dependent only on the discovery of the vaccine and the opinions of scientists, although it will constitute a truly differentiating element in the date of return, but the other element that does not Less important is the audience themselves and their desire to return to the stands again. Is it possible that the stadiums will be filled with fans again, and even if it is possible to return, the audience will never return to the same intensity, and perhaps many will refrain from it permanently (Di Fronso *et al.*, 2020).

The situation in which the public lived is a situation that we have not seen before, and this situation will shape our behaviors and thoughts again, and the panic and horror we are currently living in will create what we can call gathering phobia and hygiene obsession, and we will not be able to return to engage in large gatherings easily, so the presence will be in the midst of fifty thousand Someone to watch a match is crazy. An individual who is a sports fan may discover that he did not miss it as much as he thought,. Also, the refusal of some sports clubs during the pandemic to pay the dues and salaries of the employees generated a state of frustration and shock among their followers and fans.

The other part that everyone will not forget also is the share that football played in the spread of the virus when it

was late in closing, and perhaps this contributed to the largest tragedy of Corona in the world; The Lombardy region, which alone recorded about 5,400 deaths, according to the newspaper "Lico di Bergamo", and the beginning was a football match, attended by almost a third of the population of the city of Bergamo at San Siro Stadium, and then they returned to their town to explode the bomb of the virus that has not ended yet, and the effect did not stop at Not only Italy, but also contributed to the transmission of the virus to Spain through the Valencia mission that accompanied the team, And days after the meeting, Valencia announced that journalist Kiki Mathieu had been infected with the virus, which in turn transmitted it to his colleagues, and within days, about 35% of the accompanying mission was announced, including Gaya, Mangala and Garay, and a week later Spain was preparing to be a new Italy, and the city of Valencia alone recorded 10 thousand. condition. The impact of this event on the fans a lot. This may make a difference in their relationship with football, or at least in their decision to go to the stadiums again.

From the perspective of sports psychologists, the Olympics without fans is a realistic scientific experiment that helps researchers and clinicians to disentangle the true impact of a crowd of fans on their athletes and on the spectators at home. Global gymnastics star Simone Biles has pulled out of the women's team event from the Olympics, saying, "These Olympics have been really stressful," adding, "Overall, there's no audience, and there are a lot of different variables involved." Later, Biles also decided not to participate in individual public events "Wherever there is competition, whether on the field or in the arenas, players feel this uncertainty," says Louise Byrne, a practicing sport and exercise psychologist at Optimise Potential, a UK sports psychology consultancy. They have witnessed it before," she adds, adding that part of the problem was caused by the sudden decision not to allow spectators to attend.

The pandemic has underscored the importance of audiences to sports culture, and it explains why the compensatory methods that sports federations have adopted to solve fan absenteeism have met with varying degrees of success, says Daniel Wan, a professor of psychology at Murray State University in Kentucky who studies the science of sports. Sports Psychology and Fan Behaviour, "It's not like the NBA has a committee designed to figure out how to bring in fans when they aren't around," he adds. They could, but none of it was real for regular or professional fans." (Pillay *et al.*, 2019)

The absence of fans in person affects the advantage of the landlord, a statistically supported phenomenon, which would have benefited the competitors. Also, without fans, audio devices in the arena, stadium or stadium will have unintended consequences for players and spectators alike. predicting its content, but also the talk between rulers, and perhaps most embarrassingly, the swear words that were not meant to be heard (Kuettel & Larsen, 2020).

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6- EFFECTS OF COVID 19 ON THE SPORTS INDUSTRY

There are many concepts for the sports industry, some of which see it as the market with an economic dimension that is presented to consumers products, services, places, and ideas related to sport, fitness, or leisure (global-igi ,2020; global-igi, either as a broad definition, it is an industry in which people, activities, businesses, and organizations participate in the production, facilitation or Promote or organize any sport-focused activity, experience or commercial enterprise (Somoggi, 2020).

It is the market in which the commercial activities or products offered to buyers are related to sports and may be goods, services, people, places or ideas. Globally, sports have become an industry that generates money and large incomes for societies, clubs, and individuals. This industry has created and creates excellent opportunities for creative youth. The player who excels in football, basketball, tennis, golf, baseball, or globally and regionally, volleyball, or others, gets rewarding salaries and privileges, much more than what his peers get in the fields of work in different sectors. Covid-19, as a global pandemic, poses a great danger to people's lives, and a threat to the interests of countries and economic institutions, and it has had great effects on economies in various countries of the world. The suspension of all sports activities at the level of clubs and tournaments, and the postponement of most sporting events to later dates. And despite the modest return of some tournaments without fans, now this matter is not enough to return the spirit to the sports industry because the largest income from it comes from follow-up and attracting the consumer, which necessitated the development of strategies to confront it after the semi-adaptation that occurred after the shock, and this pandemic has future positives. to similar situations and crises in order to create a strategy for managing the situation and confronting it while such a situation is repeated at the global or regional level (The European Platform for Sport Innovation (EPSI, 2020)].

7- RISKS ASSOCIATED WITH THE IMPACT OF THE CORONA VIRUS IN THE SPORTS FIELD

There are many dangers that the Corona virus has imposed on sports, as shown in Figure 1

1- Economic risks:

The CEO of Bayern Munich reports that the financial and economic impact of the major clubs due to the threat of the virus epidemic.

Corona will increase the financial financing deficit for these clubs because they depend on match revenues, fans and broadcasting rights.

The television broadcast for these matches (Betar& Kots, 2020).

The Stoke City club president confirms that the contracts for television broadcasting of football matches, and the revenues from attending matches, will be suspended commercial activities, the media, and sponsorship rights, will increase the losses to these English clubs and will the loss also reaches third-degree clubs(Betar & Kots . 2020)

The Olympic Committee indicated that the Olympic torch relay in Greece would be halted, for fear of the spread of the Corona virus, after it attracted Torch relay large numbers of audience, and the postponement of the Tokyo Summer Olympics

2- Political and legal risks

Through the cessation of sports activity in general and the financial losses that will be incurred by the major clubs, and this will lead to losses for the players, technicians, coaches or workers of these clubs. To cut salaries either, and we find that there is no implementation of the conditions sponsorship, television rights, or even the sale of match tickets (Betar ,& Kots , 2020).

3- Social and psychological risks:

The lack of going to sports clubs and practicing sports activities that are popular with individuals, as well as parks public parks and recreational activities will worsen their psychological and social condition and they must Light physical exercises at home (Sobhy, 2020).

4- Health and physical risks:

It is well known that everyone must sit at home, stay away from gatherings as much as possible, and not go outside the home is only for essential needs, whether it is for the players or for the activities this will worsen the physical condition either recreational clubs, parks or public gardens. We find that most sports equipment is more susceptible to this virus for the use of more than one person, and therefore it must be sterilized.

All sports equipment, all clubs, all floors, seats, and walls, because this virus is spreading fast, and I must It will also cause harm to everyone. Commitment to sitting at home, and this means that I will have to gain weight, whether it is for players or others, due to a lack of their practice of sports activities, and the lack of sports equipment and tools at home (Betar & Kots, 2020).

Figure 1: Effects of the Coronavirus (Covid-19) In the sports field

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